

Electrochemical synthesis of dendritic nanosized conductive polythiophene cobalt composite as charge storage device

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Abstract : We report electrochemical synthesis of hyperbranched dendritic polythiophene cobalt composite via *in situ* electropolymerization from a solution of thiophene, perchloric acid, cobalt(II) chloride and acetonitrile using an electrode set up consisting of a vertical anode and circular cathode to provide uniform electrical field. Fractal dimension of front views of growth patterns of the thiophene cobalt composite were calculated by box counting method and found in the range 1.81–1.86. Morphology and growth kinetic studies of the composites were made and characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), powder X-ray diffraction studies (XRD), thermogravimetric studies (TG/DTG), electrical conductivity measurements and charge-discharge experiments. Electron spin resonance (ESR), scanning electron microscopy with Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) gave evidence for encapsulation of Co^{II} in the composite. XRD and TEM studies revealed the formation of nanosized polythiophene cobalt composite of size < 100 nm. Electropolymerization proceeds through electrochemical steps including the oxidation of monomer to form radical cation.

Keywords : Electrochemical polymerization, composite, nanomaterials, conductive polymer, TEM, SEM-EDS, ESR.

Introduction

Conducting polymers with large π -conjugated structure have received considerable attention due to their potential applications in chemical and biological sensors, rechargeable batteries, light emitting diodes, corrosion resistance etc.^{1–3}. Conducting polymers are also reported as active materials in electrochemical capacitors⁴. Enzymatic reaction based synthesis of conducting polymer polythiophene was carried out by Krikstolaityte *et al.*⁵. Electrochemically synthesized polymers have been widely used in molecular imprinting for chemical sensing⁶. Suitable modifications in these materials may improve their applicability. It is possible by preparing hybrid materials containing inorganic and organic oxides or salts to give rise composites^{7,8}. Conducting polymers can be synthesized either chemically or electrochemically. Method of electrochemical synthesis is most common as it is simple, quick and perfectly controllable⁹. Conducting polymers with metals incorporated into the polymer structure are

known as conducting metallo-polymers or metal composites. Metal-containing conducting polymers are a new and interesting class of materials that combine some of the redox properties of conducting polymers and some of those metal ions¹⁰.

Among these polymers, thiophene based materials have emerged as one of the most promising materials due to the ease in synthesis, its environmental stability and the possibility to modify it with different chemical groups^{11,12}. Temperature dependence studies of electric and dielectric properties of polythiophene based nanocomposites are reported by Tiwari *et al.*¹³.

In the present paper, we report synthesis of hyperbranched dendritic polythiophene cobalt composite via *in situ* electropolymerization at room temperature and its characterization by TEM, XRD, TG/DTG, ESR and SEM-EDS electrical conductivity measurements and its charging-discharging properties, fractal dimension calculation and growth kinetic studies.

Experimental

Thiophene (Spectrochem), perchloric acid 70% (s.d. fine chem. Ltd., AR), cupric chloride (Qualigens, AR), acetonitrile (s.d. fine chem. Ltd., LR) and milli-Q water were used as such.

Development of dendritic polymers by electropolymerization :

Cobalt composite of polythiophene was electrochemically synthesized by anodic oxidation from the system thiophene, acetonitrile, perchloric acid and cobalt chloride under potentiostatic condition. The electrochemical synthesis of polymer was carried out using an experimental set-up described earlier¹⁴. 10 mL of a solution of thiophene and perchloric acid in presence of cobalt chloride in acetonitrile was taken in petri dish. Cleaned platinum vertical anode (diameter 0.4 mm) and a circular platinum cathode were used in electropolymerization. The vertical anode was put at the centre of circular cathode such as to touch the air/liquid interface. These electrodes were attached to potentiostat (Scientific India). Polymerization started at the anode as soon as the potential was applied across the electrodes and growth patterns were obtained. The aggregates were washed properly and dried in vacuum desiccator. Photographs of two dimensional views of patterns were taken using a NIKON camera. Morphologies of polythiophene cobalt composites at different time are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Fractal dimension were calculated by box counting method as described earlier¹⁵.

Growth of polymerization was studied by recording weight of polymer aggregates at different time with varying concentrations of cobalt chloride and field intensities. Results are shown in Figs. 1-3.

Electrical conductivity measurement :

Solid polymer aggregates filled in the capillary as described earlier¹⁶ and electrical conductivity was measured by two probe technique. Results are shown in Fig. 4.

Charge-discharge experiment :

Charge-discharge behaviour of polythiophene and polythiophene cobalt composite was studied by using an experimental setup shown in Fig. 5(a). The solid material (5 mm in length) was put in a glass capillary of radius 0.1 cm and connected with platinum electrodes (P_1 and P_2). DC voltage (2 V) was applied across the material through

a potentiostat (P). The potential was generated in the polymer aggregates were measured at different time intervals. At the time of potential measurement across the electrodes, the potentiostat (P) was switched off. Results are shown in Fig. 5(b).

To study the discharge behavior, the potentiostat was removed from the circuit and potential across the electrodes was measured as a function of time. Results are recorded in Fig. 5(c). The experiment was carried out for polythiophene as well as polythiophene cobalt composite containing cobalt chloride for comparison.

Powder X-ray diffraction studies :

Powder X-ray diffraction pattern of polythiophene cobalt composite was taken using CuK_{α} radiation from IIT Delhi. Result is shown in Fig. 7. Crystallite size was calculated by using Debye Scherrer formula.

TG/DTG studies :

TG/DTG study of polymer composite was carried out upto 700 °C from STIC Cochin. Results are shown in Fig. 8.

Electron spin resonance (ESR) studies :

ESR study of polythiophene cobalt composite was carried out using Mn as a reference material. Spectrum was taken from IIT Bombay. ESR spectrum is shown in Fig. 9.

SEM-EDS studies :

SEM-EDS studies of the composite were carried out using EDS model 5-ADD0048 at the resolution 5.9 KeV from Central Instrument Facility, IIT, BHU, Varanasi. Results are shown in Fig. 10 and recorded in Table 3. Scanning electron microscopic studies of the composite were carried out using Zeiss EVO/18 Research instrument. Results are shown in Fig. 11.

Transmission electron microscopic studies (TEM) :

TEM images of electropolymerized thiophene cobalt composite were taken using a Philips Transmission Electron Microscope (Model CM 200). Results are shown in Fig. 12.

Results and discussion

Polythiophene cobalt composite was electrochemically polymerized from thiophene-acetonitrile-perchloric acid-cobalt chloride obtained on a platinum vertical anode. Platinum circular cathode was used to provide a uniform electric field around the anode. Two dimensional views of polythiophene cobalt composites obtained at different co-

(A)

(B)

Fig. 1. (A) Growth patterns of polythiophene cobalt composites obtained during electropolymerization at different time of polymerization and cobalt chloride concentrations. Conditions : [Thiophene] = 1.5 M, [HClO₄] = 0.1 M, [CoCl₂.6H₂O] = 0.0006 M (a-f), 0.0010 M (g-l), 0.0015 M (m-r). Field intensity = 3.6 V/cm. (B) Plots showing weight of polythiophene cobalt composites at different time for different values of cobalt chloride concentrations (Fig 1B). (i) 0006 M, (ii) 0.0010 M, (iii) 0.0015 M. Other conditions are given in the caption of Fig. 1(A).

balt chloride concentrations and field intensities at varying time intervals are shown in Figs. 1(A) and 2(A) respectively.

Fractal dimension of images shown in Figs. 2A (m-r) were calculated by box counting method. The total number of pixels $N(r)$ of radius r is related by the relationship

$N(r) \sim r^D$. The fractal dimension (D) was calculated for images obtained at different time from the plot of $\log N(r)$ versus $\log r$. Results are recorded in Table 1. The values of D lie in the range 1.81–1.86 which is in agreement with the values of Diffusion Limited Aggregation (DLA) model. Weight of polythiophene cobalt composite was

Field intensity (V/cm)	Time (min)					
	3	5	8	10	15	30
2.4	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)
3.6	(g)	(h)	(i)	(j)	(k)	(l)
4.8	(m)	(n)	(o)	(p)	(q)	(r)

(A)

(B)

Fig. 2. (A) Growth patterns of polythiophene cobalt composites obtained during electropolymerization at different time (3–30 min). Conditions : [Thiophene] = 1.5 M, [HClO₄] = 0.1 M, [CoCl₂·6H₂O] = 0.0008 M. Field intensity = 2.4 V/cm (a-f), 3.6 V/cm (g-l) and 4.8 V/cm (m-r). (B) Plots showing weight of polythiophene cobalt composites obtained at different time for different values of field intensity as shown in Fig. 2(A). Field intensity = 2.4, 3.6 and 4.8 V/cm (curves i-iii respectively).

Table 1. Values of fractal dimension D of 2-D views of composites shown in Fig. 2A (m-r)
Field intensity = 4.8 V/cm

Time (min)	Fractal dimension (D)	Correlation coefficient (R)
3	1.86	0.998
5	1.86	0.997
8	1.84	0.997
10	1.82	0.996
15	1.82	0.992
30	1.81	0.991

was found to increase non linearly with time as shown in Fig. 1B. Dependence of field intensity on growth pattern and corresponding weight of polymer aggregates at different time are shown in Fig. 2. Experiment was also carried out at different cobalt chloride concentrations keeping other parameter fixed. Results are shown in Fig. 3. TG/DTG curves of polythiophene cobalt composite are shown in Fig. 8 and was found to be more stable as compared to polythiophene.

(A)

(B)

Fig. 3. (A) Growth patterns of polythiophene cobalt composite obtained during electropolymerization at different cobalt chloride concentrations. Conditions : [Thiophene] = 1.5 M, [HClO₄] = 0.1 M, [CoCl₂.6H₂O] = 0–0.0016 M (a-h) respectively. Field intensity = 3.6 V/cm. (B) Plots showing weight of polythiophene cobalt composites obtained at different values of cobalt chloride concentrations as shown in Fig. 3(A).

measured at different time, keeping other parameters fixed. When the experiment was carried out at different cobalt chloride concentrations, weight of the polymer aggregate

SEM and TEM images of polythiophene cobalt composite are shown in Figs. 11 and 12 respectively. SEM images show spherical cauliflower like structure. TEM

result reveal that many particles of polythiophene cobalt composite have diameters in the range 50–100 nm. It is in agreement with the value of crystallite size (~35 nm) obtained by using Debye Scherrer formula¹⁷.

$$t = \frac{0.9\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \cdot \frac{360}{2\pi} \text{ \AA}$$

where λ = wavelength of X-ray (1.5418 Å), β = half maximum line breadth and θ = Bragg's angle.

In the presence of electric field, oxidation of monomer takes place at the surface of the electrode to form the radical cation which is further stabilized by resonance :

The electron thus released is associated with the H^+ ions at the cathode as described earlier¹⁸.

As evident by evolution of bubbles at cathode.

The next step involves radical cation coupling. The radical cation having greater unpaired electron density at the α position reacts with other radical cation of the monomer to form a dimer.

The dimer obtained during the electropolymerization was further oxidized to the dimer radical cation with greater electron density at the α position. It reacts with the other radical cation of monomer to form a trimer. The process is repeated again and again resulting in the formation of polymer. The electropolymerization gives the neutral conductive polymer by doping of anions (Cl^- , ClO_4^-) as shown below :

In addition to α - α' linkage in polythiophene, some α - β linkage can also take place similar to polypyrrole¹⁹.

It can lead to greater random motion of radical cation leading to the formation of complex dendritic patterns.

Polythiophene composite was electrodeposited from a solution containing thiophene, cobalt chloride as the source of metal ion. During this process the cobalt metal ion is encapsulated in polythiophene matrix as reported for encapsulation of metal ion in dendrimer²⁰. The presence of cobalt in the composite is evident by ESR (Fig. 9) and SEM-EDS (Fig. 10, Table 3) studies. The ESR spectrum shows a single peak corresponding to Co^{II} . The signal for the reference is not shown in the spectrum.

Fig. 4. Plot of electrical conductivity of polythiophene cobalt composites versus cobalt chloride concentrations at 30.0 ± 0.1 °C. Conditions : [Thiophene] = 1.5 M, $[HClO_4]$ = 0.1 M, $[CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O]$ = 0, 0.6, 1.0 and 1.5 mM. Time of electropolymerization = 30 min. Field intensity = 3.6 V/cm.

Electrical conductivity (σ) was measured in the solid state and found to increase linearly with concentration of Co^{2+} (Fig. 4) obeying an empirical equation $\sigma = m [Co^{2+}]$

Fig. 5. (a) Experimental setup employed for charging and discharging of polythiophene and polythiophene cobalt composites. Thickness of polymer aggregates = 5 mm, P₁, P₂ = Platinum electrodes, MM = multimeter and P = potentiostat. Diameter of the capillary = 2 mm, applied voltage across the electrodes = 2 V. Values DC potential developed as a function of time during charging and discharging processes (b and c respectively) for polythiophene (curve i) and polythiophene cobalt composites (curves ii-iv). Conditions : [Thiophene] = 1.5 M, [HClO₄] = 0.1 M, [CoCl₂.6H₂O] = 0, 0.0006, 0.0010 and 0.0015 M (curves i-iv respectively).

Table 2. Dependence of potential developed (V) on time (t) during the charging process at different cobalt chloride concentrations obeying an empirical equation $V = mt^{-1} + c$. Applied voltage across the material = 2 V. Conditions are same as indicated in caption of Fig. 5

[Co ²⁺] (M)	Time (min)	Voltage (mV)	Slope (m)	Intercept (c)	Correlation coefficient (R)
0.0000	1	5	-0.011	0.016	0.982
	2	9			
	3	15			
	4	16			
	5	16			
0.0006	1	52	-0.022	0.075	0.992
	2	66			
	3	72			
	4	74			
	5	74			
0.0010	1	62	-0.024	0.087	0.989
	2	78			
	3	85			
	4	86			
	5	86			
0.0015	1	72	-0.022	0.096	0.969
	2	89			
	3	92			
	4	95			
	5	95			

Table 3. SEM-EDS data for polythiophene cobalt composite Conditions : [Thiophene] = 1.5 M, [HClO₄] = 0.1 M, [Cobalt chloride] = 0.0006 M, in acetonitrile medium. Field intensity = 3.6 V/cm, Time of polymerization = 30 min

Element	Weight (%)	Atomic (%)
O	35.01	52.60
S	50.01	37.49
Cl	14.08	9.55
Co	0.90	0.37
Total	100.00	

+ c where m and c are slope and intercept respectively. The correlation coefficient value was found to be 0.995. Similar trend was also observed by Zhu *et al.*²¹ for conducting polymetallorotaxanes while electrochemical inclusion of Cu²⁺ in the composite was reported by Gourier *et al.*²².

Charge-discharge behavior of polythiophene and polythiophene cobalt composite was studied using a simple

Fig. 6. Plot of DC voltage (V) developed as a function of time⁻¹ during the charging process as shown in Fig. 5(b) for (i) polythiophene and (ii-iv) polythiophene cobalt composites as indicated in the caption of Fig. 5(a).

Fig. 7. PXRD curve for the polythiophene cobalt composite. Conditions : [Thiophene] = 1.5 M, [HClO₄] = 0.1 M, [CoCl₂.6H₂O] = 0.0006 M, field intensity = 3.6 V/cm. Time of electropolymerization = 30 min.

experimental setup shown in Fig. 5(a). The potential generated as a function of time in systems polythiophene (curve a) and polythiophene cobalt composite at different cobalt chloride concentrations (curves b-d) are recorded in Fig. 5b. The result for the discharge process is shown in Fig. 5(c). For the charging process, values of voltage (V) obtained at different time (*t*) follow an empirical equation $V = mt^{-1} + c$ where *m* and *c* are slope and intercept respectively. Results for polythiophene and polythiophene cobalt composite are recorted in Table 2. Polythiophene cobalt

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. (a,b) TG/DTG curves for polythiophene cobalt composite. Conditions are same as given in caption of Fig. 7.

composites show higher charging property than polythiophene. Electrical conductivity also follows the same trend as shown in Fig. 4. Potential difference is created in the conducting materials and attains a constant value which decreases with time on removing the applied potential from the circuit (Fig. 5). It shows the charging-discharging behavior in an electrochemical system which may be useful for charge storage applications.

Conclusion

New results on electrochemical synthesis of dendritic conductive polythiophene cobalt composite using an electrode set up consisting of a vertical anode and circular cathode are reported. Fractal dimension of two dimensional views of polymer aggregates were calculated and results are reported. Growth kinetics studies have been carried out by measuring weight of polymer aggregate as a function of time at different field intensites and cobalt chloride concentrations were made. Polymer aggregates

Fig. 9. ESR spectrum of polythiophene cobalt composite. Conditions : [Thiophene] = 1.5 M, [HClO₄] = 0.1 M, [CoCl₂·6H₂O] = 0.0006 M. Field intensity = 3.6 V/cm. Time of electropolymerization = 30 min.

Fig. 10. SEM-EDX measurement polythiophene cobalt composite. Conditions are the same as indicated in caption of Fig. 9.

Fig. 11. SEM images of polythiophene cobalt composite. Conditions are the same as indicated in caption of Fig. 9.

were characterized by SEM, TEM, TG/DTG, XRD studies, electrical conductivity measurements and charge-discharge properties. ESR and SEM-EDS studies indicated the encapsulation of Co^{II} in the composite. Electrical con-

Fig. 12. TEM images of polythiophene cobalt composite. Conditions are the same as indicated in caption of Fig. 9.

ductivity of the polythiophene cobalt composite was found to depend upon concentration of cobalt chloride in the composite. The electrical conductivity (σ) of the composite increased linearly with increase in cobalt chloride concentration obeying an empirical equation $\sigma = m [\text{Co}^{2+}] + c$. ESR and SEM-EDS studies showed the presence of Co^{II} in the composite. XRD and TEM studies revealed the formation of particles in the nanosize range. Further, the growth was found to be inhibited in the presence of cobalt chloride. The composite also showed the charge-discharge behavior.

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References

1. X. G. Li, Z. Z. Hou, M. R. Huang and M. G. Moloney, *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2009, **113**, 21586.
2. A. S. Abd-El-Aziz, John Wiley and Sons, New Jersey, 2006.
3. W.-Y. Wong and P. D. Harvey, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.*, 2010, **31**, 671.
4. A. Rudge, J. Davey, I Raistrick, S. Gottesfeld and J. P. Ferraris, *J. Power Sources*, 1994, **47**, 89.
5. V. Krikstolaityte, J. Kuliesius, A. Ramanaviciene, L. Mikoliunaite, A. Kausaite-Minkstimiene, Y. Oztekin and A. Ramanavicius, *Polymer*, 2014, **55**, 1613.
6. P. S. Sharma, A. Pietrzyk-Le, F. D'Souza and W. Kutner, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2012, **402**, 3177.
7. A. Bhattacharya, S. De, S. N. Bhattacharya and S. Das, *J. Phys. Cond. Matter.*, 1994, **6**, 10499.

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8. W. Chen, L. Xingwei, X. Gi, W. Zhaoquang and Z. Wenqing, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, 2003, **218**, 216.
9. R. N. Singh, Madhu and R. Awasthi, *Russ. J. Electrochem.*, 2011, **40**, 317.
10. A. S. Abd-El-Aziz, S. Sezgin Dalgakiran and L. Bichler, *European Polymer Journal*, 2012, **48**, 1901.
11. I. F. Perepichka, D. F. Perepichka, H. Meng and F. Wudl, *Adv. Mater.*, 2005, **17**, 2281.
12. J. Roncali, *Chem. Rev.*, 1992, **92**, 711.
13. D. C. Tiwari, V. Sen and R. Sharma, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 2012, **50**, 49.
14. I. Das, R. Choudhary, S. K. Gupta and P. Agrawal, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2011, **115**, 8724.
15. R. P. Rastogi, I. Das, A. Pushkarna, A. Sharma, K. Jaiswal and S. Chand, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1992, **69**, A47.
16. I. Das, N. R. Agrawal, S. K. Gupta and R. P. Rastogi, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2009, **113**, 5296.
17. I. Das, PhD thesis, Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur, 1977.
18. I. Das, N. Goel, N. R. Agrawal and S. K. Gupta, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2010, **114**, 12888.
19. I. Das, N. Goel, N. R. Agrawal and S. K. Gupta, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2010, **114**, 12888.
20. M. J. Jean. Frechet, *PNAS*, 2002, **99**, 4782.
21. S. Sherry Zhu and Timothy M. Swager, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **119**, 12586.
22. D. Gourier and G. Tourillon, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1986, **90**, 5561.

